

Technological, Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (TPACK) among the Secondary Math Teachers

Kristoffer Paulo L. Ramirez, Florencia P. Paragua

Sta. Marcela National High School, San Carlos, Sta. Marcela, Apayao, 3811

kristofferpaulo.ramirez@deped.gov.ph

florencia.paragua001@deped.gov.ph

Abstract

Integrating digital technologies has a significant positive effect on content and pedagogy. This study was conducted to create a new perspective and understanding on the extent of Technological, Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (TPACK) among secondary Math teachers to address key instructional domains. It utilized a descriptive – correlational design employing a total of 26 Math teachers. The teachers filled in a survey questionnaire to describe their understanding of TPACK through the given knowledge indicators: Technological Knowledge (TK), Pedagogical Knowledge (PK), Content Knowledge (CK), Technological Pedagogical Knowledge (TPK), Technological Content Knowledge (TCK), Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK) and TPACK. With the given knowledge components, teachers registered a fair extent of TCK; other components are within the range of high extent. PK registered the highest. Statistical test between the teacher's profile and the overall mean implied that teachers who attended training more frequently tend to have higher extent of TPACK. Further test revealed that there is a correlation between the frequency of training and on TCK (medium), PCK (strong) and TPK (strong) implying a need of training for development and enhancement. Other tests indicated that there is a negative correlation on generation year and TK indicating that "older" teachers tend to have lower confidence on the use of technology in the classroom. Also, teaching experiences when tested with the latter resulted to positive correlation suggesting that TK could be developed with constant use and experiences.

Keywords: teacher profile, technological literacy, training